

DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON A PERSONAL LEARNING TRAJECTORY

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Abstract. *In the article, the development of educational technologies based on the trajectory of personal education focuses on the development of the student's personality and self-development in the teacher's activity, as well as the manifestation and realization of the students' potential in accordance with the interests, readiness, abilities and psychophysiological characteristics of the students through these technologies.*

Keywords: *preparation, development, improvement, development, upbringing, explanation, trajectory, potential.*

A student's personal educational trajectory is a direction (route) chosen by the student and which gives him the opportunity to sequentially accumulate knowledge and acquire the desired set of competencies. Learning trajectories are structured using institutional documents and guidelines, and different learning trajectories can lead to the same qualification. In the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 824 of December 31, 2020, in accordance with the curriculum and the list of elective subjects, the formation of the personal educational trajectory of each student under the supervision of the educational and methodical department (management) and the dean of the faculty with the help of a group coach is recognized as one of the stages of planning the educational process .

A personal educational trajectory is a personal path, a certain sequence of elements or a direction for the implementation of individual educational activities of a student. The development of educational technologies based on the personal learning trajectory is used in the teacher's work to develop the student's personality and self-development, and through these technologies to create conditions for the manifestation and realization of the students' potential in accordance with their interests, readiness, abilities and psychophysiological characteristics. In the development of these technologies, special attention is paid to the following issues.

For example, in the design of the content of training sessions, courses, programs, the educational standard is analyzed in order to determine the directions and limits of the use of science material as the basis of personal development at different educational stages. Consider the educational subject as a goal in the process of setting goals; work is carried out to describe a specific model of pedagogical interaction between a teacher and a student within a certain discipline and taking into account their personal capabilities. The educational material is analyzed in relation to the specific features of its subject content and organization, teacher's capabilities and pedagogical abilities, and specific features of its mastery by the student.

It is planned to include personal experience, students' experience, problematic and current issues, conditions for the development of the student's cognitive and personal sphere in the educational content.

When developing such an educational technology, the following sequence of actions is performed:

1. The formation of the diagnostic goal of education according to the characteristics of the educational subject, which reflects the goals of training in this subject (forming ..., absorbing ..., developing ..., improving ..., expanding ..., teaching ..., putting .., introduction..., development..., upbringing... etc.), requirements for the level of preparation at educational stages (explain..., show..., know..., compare. ..., be able to do..., perform..., correctly estimate..., measure..., have an idea..., build..., implement..., calculate..., recognize and use. .., construct..., describe..., use correctly..., understand and use..., decide..., understand and prove..., describe..., use... , describing..., creating..., characterizing..., mastering..., illuminating..., correct arrangement..., reading and interpreting..., explaining the meaning... etc.).

2. Determining the type of mental development of students: diagnosis of learning, development, upbringing (formation of motivation for knowledge, self-esteem, etc.).

3. Determining the level and quality of software-methodological support of science.

4. Proposing hypotheses about the options for achieving the goals (at this stage they can serve as "internal" guidelines for the development of a specific technology model).

5. Psychological and didactic analysis of methodical science presentation of educational subjects.

6. To concretize the methodical science presentation of the science related to the type of intellectual development of students.

7. Selection or development of the training course program depending on the type of mental development of students.

8. Individualization of pedagogical technology by choosing educational methods and methods that are personally relevant, well mastered and suitable for individual style.

9. Development of diagnostic tools for the process of assimilation of educational material by students.

Taking into account the uniqueness of personal experience and its active nature, dialogicity, creativity, the choice of educational and behavioral content and methods in the technology of organizing classes and educational practice, attention is paid to creating conditions for activating the experiences of educational subjects in personal tasks based on personal experience. In order to include the subjective life experience of students in the educational content, conditions are created for discussions, dialogues, imitation of life situations, interpretation of ambiguous educational text, creative problem solving, etc. Students search for information and principles, freely and independently choose methods and tools for solving problems related to discussion of work results with peers.

Depending on the student's types of thinking, personal characteristics and interests, the choice of educational work and methods of solving problems such as a schedule, scheme, abstract, research assignment is provided. The educational process is built in the zone of its immediate development.

The educational process is organized as a cycle, which includes the reflexive activity of problem situation, situation analysis, problem setting, problem solving, solution method and self-change. Conditions are created for students to constantly test their intellectual, physical, and moral strength in order to determine the problems that arise in reality and to determine their ability to solve them through joint efforts and performance of various social roles. Also, cooperative

learning; project method; multi-level education; portfolio; individual and differentiated approach in education; new pedagogical technologies such as the possibility of reflection are used.

Information and communication technologies are actively used in the organization of student activities, in the organization and conduct of classes, in conducting observations and experiments, in drawing up tables summarizing the system, structural and logical schemes. Free access to the necessary information is organized not only in information centers, but also in scientific, cultural, and information centers around the world to form an independent but reasonable opinion on a specific problem, and its extensive research opportunities are opened.

Students' achievements are monitored by determining the criteria for the effective organization of person-oriented education - the parameters of personal development (for example, changing personal tasks according to V.V. Serikov [3] or the level of learning material according to V.P. Bepalko [2] and others, etc.) will be done. Means, methods and instructions are selected to diagnose the initial state of the object, the change of which is projected. It is appropriate to use modeling methods in the organization of student achievement monitoring.

Psychological and pedagogical support of students begins with a positive assessment of their achievements. Students' beliefs about the importance of their role in the implementation of educational activities are formed. By creating an environment of mutual understanding, cooperation, respect for other opinions, lack of competition, self-awareness and recognition by others, everyone is responsible for their own choices, conditions for intersubjective communication are created.

The influence of one's own "I", the personal experience of the teacher as a partner and partner in the joint activity with the student, the influence on the formation of the worldview, the world, science and others, self-awareness, self-development, adaptation, self-management, self-protection, self educational skills develop. To support the student's personal development, he is provided with the necessary freedom to make independent decisions.

Based on the theoretical rules discussed above, we can say that the trajectory of personal education is one of the most important pedagogical concepts.

"Personal education trajectory" makes certain demands on the education system:

- to ensure equal access to full quality education according to the abilities, individual inclinations, interests and needs of all categories of students;

- to preserve the quality of education in its fundamentals and to ensure compliance with the current and future needs of the individual, society and the state, focusing on individualization of education and socialization of students, including taking into account the real needs of the labor market;

- ensuring the flexibility and variability of educational programs, the possibility of building an individual educational trajectory by the student;

- to ensure the emergence of students' own activities, their participation in the formation of their own educational content, to create conditions for self-development, independent education, self-education, self-determination and self-awareness;

- to ensure the introduction of person-oriented technologies and educational methods.

The analysis of regulatory legal documents (state educational standards of teacher training, programs on academic subjects, teacher training programs, etc.), actual educational practice in pedagogical higher education institutions, advanced training courses shows that the existing professional training of teachers in modern pedagogical education is mainly based on the teacher's

own professional aimed at partially forming their readiness to use personal-oriented technologies in their activities. This also indicates that the professional training of teachers is insufficient, which significantly hinders the implementation of education, taking into account the personal educational trajectory of the student.

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